

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.4

2nd Midterm Project Dissemination Impact Assessment Report

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D6.4
Deliverable name	2nd Midterm Project Dissemination Impact Assessment Report
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP6
Due date	30.04.2024
Version	1.0
Actual submission date	30.04.2024

Responsible organisation	Laurea University of Applied Sciences
Editor(s)	Artmir Galica (LAUREA)
Contributor(s)	Katja Silvasti (LAUREA)
Reviewers(s)	CENTRIC

Disclaimer	<p>Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate; however, the Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.</p> <p>This document reflects only the view of its authors. Neither the project partners nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The use of the content provided is at the sole risk of the user. The reader is encouraged to investigate whether professional advice is necessary in all situations.</p>
-------------------	--

DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	29/10/2023	Draft	Artmir Galica (LAUREA)	Initial Draft
0.3	02/04/2024	Draft	Katja Silvasti (LAUREA)	Review/Edit
0.4	08/04/2024	Draft	Artmir Galica (LAUREA)	Review/Edit
0.5	19/04/2024 – 25/04/2024	Draft	CENTRIC	Review by Partners
1.0	30/04/2024	Final	Rashel Talukder and Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)	Final approval and submission

Table of Contents

- 1. Introduction 5
- 2. Overview of Dissemination and Communication Activities 6
 - Summary of Dissemination Activities 6
 - 2.1. Dissemination Events 7
 - 2.2. Dissemination materials, channels and related statistics 12
- 3. Dissemination KPIs Analysis 27
- 4. Conclusion and future recommendations 30
 - List of Figures 31
 - List of Tables 31

1. Introduction

This document is part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package - WP6, and it outlines project dissemination activities and the overall key performance indicators (KPIs) reached over the second reporting period, as defined in the dissemination and communication plan. The dissemination impact assessment will serve as a form of self-evaluation that supports the review of reached KPIs and overall performance of the dissemination efforts.

The document includes the following sections:

- Section 1: Overview of Dissemination Activities
- Section 2: Analysis of Dissemination KPIs
- Section 3: Conclusions and Future Recommendations

Key changes since the 1st Midterm Project Dissemination Impact assessment report include the following:

- The CYCLOPES community has grown substantially and the number of members - organisations and individual members - has more than doubled during this reporting period.
- Social media channels are reaching more audience than before and posting is more frequent and structured.
- Number of newsletter subscribers has tripled and newsletter will be produced quarterly instead of bi-annually.
- CYCLOPES will establish a YouTube channel which will be used to host video content and podcasts.
- A new online form has been developed for our partners to submit information on their dissemination activities.
- CYCLOPES has established a partnership with NOTIONES project, and the collaboration in the future will include for example webinars.

2. Overview of Dissemination and Communication Activities

Summary of Dissemination Activities

The following table shows a short summary of dissemination activities performed during the second reporting period of the project.

Table 1 Summary of Dissemination Activities

No.	Activity	Number of activities	Audience reached/impressions
1	Organised Workshops	6	N/A
2	Other external workshops attendance	5	~ 450
3	Press releases (online)	0	-
4	Policy paper	1	>1000
5	Project Presentations at External Meetings	4	~ 150
6	Flyers Created (various events)	10	Not Applicable
7	Social Media posts Twitter	48	>5000
8	Social Media posts LinkedIn	82	>29775 (last 12 months)
9	Website Posts	27	22881
10	Participation to Conferences/Brokerage events	10	>3000
11	Other Publications	1	~2500
12	Organised Dissemination Events	2	150
13	Organised Joint Live Exercises	1	~40
14	Organised Webinars	1	74
15	Participation to external webinars	0	-
16	Videos	0	-
17	Leaflets created	1	-
18	External channels used i.e. networks of practitioners, result booster platforms etc.	4	~10000
19	Project cooperation membership (clustering)	20	~200
20	Newsletters	3	~1000
21	Newsletter subscribers	348	-
22	Established Cooperation with other institutions/agencies	10	-

2.1. Dissemination Events

Table 2 List of external dissemination events where CYCLOPES has been represented

	Date (DD/MM/YY)	Event	Location	Attended by	Audience type	Number of participants	Dissemination of / relevance to CYCLOPES
1	14.3.2023	CERIS workshop on Europol's new role in Horizon Europe	N/A	PPHS, UCD, SPA	Security Research Community, LEAS and 40 other project initiatives	120	Dissemination of project activities and liaising with other participants
2	14-16.3.2023	Security & Policing Event	UK	N/A	LEA,SMEs Institutions, other	N/A	Dissemination of Project Activities
3	18-20.4.2023	CYCLOPES Joint Live Exercise 2023, Cryptocurrency	Croatia	PPHS, SPA, UCD CCI, HO, LAUREA	LEAs, SMEs, Institutions, other	40	
4	28.6.2023	EACTDA Tools4LEAs	France	TNO	LEA Community	30	Dissemination of results with the CYCLOPES network and representation of the CYCLOPES project
5	24.1.2023	Tools4Leas Demonstration & Evaluation Event at EUROPOL	Netherlands	TNO	LEA Community		
6	24-25.10.2023	SRE2023	Belgium	CRI	Security research community, Policy, EC, Practitioners, NGO, Research, Academia Etc.	1255	N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669.

7	21.9.2023	2nd CYCLOPES dissemination event	online	All Consortium Members	CYCLOPES Community such as the European Law Enforcement Agencies, industry and science as well as relevant networks and organisations responsible for fighting cybercrime	100	
8	4.9.2023	EU Innovation Hub	Belgium	PPHS	Security Research community, Industry, LEAs etc.	N/A	Representing CYCLOPES project, sharing information and gathering insights etc.
9	27-28.6.2023	International Horizon Europe “Civil Security for Society” Info Days	Brussels	PPHS		N/A	Dissemination of project results/experiences
10	N/A	ENLETS NCP Meeting	Sweden	PPHS	EU Law Enforcement	35	Community of LEAs that are interested and can support CYCLOPES' actions with participation in events and workshops
11	5-7.6.2023	Cybercrime Conference #PTXXI	Poland	PPHS	representatives of LEAs and prosecutors fighting cybercrime, but also international experts, as well as companies and academia.	200	Dissemination of project results/experiences
12	19-21.9.2023	CINTiA 2023 Conference	Poland	PPHS	LEAs, industry and academia.	150	Dissemination of project results/experiences

13	28.9.2023	European Network for Financial Investigations (ENFIN) online meeting	Online	PPHS	LEAs	25	Dissemination of CYCLOPES results - presentation focused on result relevant for LEAs working on financial investigations
14	20-21.6.2023	Visit to CEPOL European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training (CEPOL)		PPHS, LAUREA, HO, AS, CENTRIC	LEAs	N/A	Dissemination and cooperation, networking between CYCLOPES and CEPOL
15	26.10.2023	Anti-FinTer Policy Seminar	Brussels	N/A	N/A	N/A	Dissemination of CYCLOPES results
16	13.3.2024	EACTDA with Polícia Judiciária, Tools4LEAs Event	Portugal	PPHS	LEAs	N/A	Dissemination of results with the CYCLOPES network and representation of the CYCLOPES project
17	13-15.12.2023	OCTOPUS Conference & Expo booth	Romania	LAUREA	LEAs, industry and academia	1000	Dissemination and communication of CYCLOPES
18	13-15.12.2023	OCTOPUS Conference presentation	Romania	LAUREA	LEAs, industry and academia	N/A	Dissemination of CYCLOPES results
19	10-11.4.2024	14th InfoCom Security 2024 Conference and Expo	Greece	IANUS Consulting	Cybersecurity professionals, IT analysts	N/A	Communication and Dissemination of CYCLOPES to a wider audience
20	16-17.4.2024	CYCLOPES 3rd Dissemination event	Austria	PPHS, All	LEAs, industry and academia	N/A	Dissemination of project results to a wider audience

21	13.3.2024	Security and policing UK event	UK	HO, CENTRIC	LEA,SMEs Institutions, other	N/A	Dissemination of Project Activities
22	29-30.11.2023	GRACE project final event	Spain	PPHS	LEAs and Grace project community	N/A	Dissemination of results, cooperation, and networking
23	7.12.2023	EJCN and CYCLOPES Webinar 'Enterprises as a victims of cybercrime'	Online	PPHS, ALL			
24	26-27.9.2023	15th Forensic Technology Days	Germany	UCD, CCI	LEA,SMEs Institutions, other		Dissemination and cooperation, networking
25	4-8.9.2023	UNCOVER Summer School and Capture the Flag (CTF) Event	Czechia	UCD, CCI	LEAs & PhD students		Dissemination and cooperation, networking

Figure 1 An example of other events where CYCLOPES participants have represented the project.

2.2. Dissemination materials, channels and related statistics

Website stats

CYCLOPES' website serves as the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results.

The website is accessible from desktop as well as mobile devices on the following address <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. It hosts publicly available content produced by the project such as relevant upcoming events, news, public deliverables, project information, network information and so on.

During the period 1.11.2022 – 17.4.2024, the project website has had the following results:

The website has been visited by 4,295 users, Served 7,720 sessions with 16,559 page views (Figure 1). A session in this case represents the time from the moment a person accesses the CYCLOPES website in the browser until the browser is closed or inactive for 30 minutes. Page views are counted as a total amount of views of all pages during such sessions.

Website analytics data page views and unique visitors:

● Home - CYCLOPES Project ● Events - CYCLOPES Project ● CYCLOPES Dissemination Event < >

Q Search... Rows per page: 10 Go to: 1 < 1-10 of 127 >

Page title and screen class	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count	Key events
	100% of total	100% of total	Avg 0%	Avg 0%	100% of total	
	16,559	4,292	3.86	1m 14s	44,848	0.00
1 Home - CYCLOPES Project	5,245	2,456	2.14	29s	17,014	0.00
2 Events - CYCLOPES Project	1,032	460	2.24	37s	1,856	0.00
3 CYCLOPES Dissemination Event, Vienna, Austria 16th-17th April, 2024 - CYCLOPES Project	1,019	414	2.46	52s	3,200	0.00
4 About Us - CYCLOPES Project	939	593	1.58	53s	2,651	0.00
5 Partners - CYCLOPES Project	823	366	2.25	1m 08s	2,439	0.00
6 News - CYCLOPES Project	805	250	3.22	41s	1,308	0.00
7 2023 Joint Live Exercises: Croatia, April - CYCLOPES Project	758	340	2.23	55s	2,128	0.00
8 Join US - CYCLOPES Project	731	396	1.85	45s	1,820	0.00
9 Downloads - CYCLOPES Project	679	371	1.83	38s	1,701	0.00
10 Contact - CYCLOPES Project	389	285	1.36	12s	992	0.00

Figure 2 Overall website audience analytics

Country ▾ +		↓ Users
		4,292 100% of total
1	United States	623
2	United Kingdom	543
3	Netherlands	337
4	Germany	298
5	Poland	298
6	Spain	201
7	Ireland	190
8	Austria	171
9	Finland	147
10	France	138

Figure 3 Overall audience of the website by country

Leaflets

During the reporting period CYCLOPES project has used two main leaflets (Figure 3). One containing overall project information i.e. summary of project objectives, partners and overall work. This is produced in two versions: online and print. The project leaflet has been updated with new schedule for events. The second leaflet is created for the CYCLOPES network community. The latter contains information related to joining the network, guide, benefits of joining and a call to action.

The leaflet has been published to all relevant channels inc. external networks and conferences where the consortium participates. The consortium is encouraged to share copies of leaflets in various events where they participate.

Project leaflet

Network leaflet

CYBERCRIME LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK

THE PROJECT
The CYCLOPES project builds and maintains an international network of law enforcement agencies (LEA) combating cybercrime. We identify solutions and research activities that help build the capability of cybercrime - related entities provide for identification and communication for incident investigation and incident response.

OBJECTIVES

- To have a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime
- To define a clear capability gaps and requirements of practitioners fighting cybercrime
- To explore the development of new technologies, research activities and resources applied to combating cybercrime
- To explore practices regarding domain registration and associated systems
- To cooperate with other networks of practitioners and relevant stakeholders fighting cybercrime
- To increase the visibility of the CYCLOPES network to enlarge its stakeholder community and increase its impact
- To analyse current, critical and legal challenges related to cybercrime

KEY PARTNERS & NETWORKS
CYCLOPES unites the subjects of other relevant cybercrime and networks - complementing, building, activities within their operating spheres. The results and outcomes will act as a springboard for future actions that harmonize, where possible, with existing networks and organisations also aiming to end the fight against cybercrime in Europe. Key partners and networks for CYCLOPES include:

IDENTIFYING GAPS, NEEDS AND CAPABILITIES
Every year, 3 workshops will be organized with each workshop dedicated to different domains fighting cybercrime: 1) Cybercrime affecting people directly; 2) Cybercrime affecting critical systems; 3) Digital forensics. The groups below illustrate the planned topics for the year 2023. At the end of each year, new topics for each domain will be chosen.

LEAs - JOIN THE NETWORK ACADEMIA AND INDUSTRY - SUBMIT YOUR SOLUTION

WE NEED YOUR HELP, PLEASE GET IN TOUCH!
We seek coordinators from LEAs, the Academia & Research (Academy) who share an interest and wish to contribute to different thematic subjects in the project.

JOIN THE CYBERCRIME LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK

GET INVOLVED IN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY
The CYCLOPES project builds and maintains an international network of law enforcement agencies (LEA) combating cybercrime. We identify solutions and research activities that help build the capability of cybercrime - related entities provide for identification and communication for incident investigation and incident response.

WHY JOIN?
By becoming a CYCLOPES Community Member, you join the CYCLOPES network of other partners (including LEA practitioners) and the existing collaborative efforts with other networks and organisations also aiming to end the fight against cybercrime in Europe. Key partners and networks for CYCLOPES include: EUROPOL, FRILETS, CYCLOS, EUCISA, LEADS, EUCOM, EuroCERT, CIB and 13 European LEA practitioners from UK, Poland, Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Croatia, Bulgaria, Latvia, Belgium and Italy from a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime.

WHO CAN JOIN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY?
We seek to build and maintain an international network of European law enforcement agencies combating cybercrime with the involvement of other law practitioners to share knowledge and expertise. The CYCLOPES Community is therefore looking for the following types of cybercrime-related practitioners to get involved:

COMMUNITY MEMBERS' BENEFITS
Every year, 3 workshops will be organized with each workshop dedicated to different domains fighting cybercrime: 1) Cybercrime affecting people directly; 2) Cybercrime affecting critical systems; 3) Digital forensics.

HOW TO JOIN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY?
By joining the CYCLOPES Community, you can participate in the dedicated workshops, gain first-hand experience, attend seminars and courses, and more. You will also connect with practitioners with specialist and experts and have first-hand access to information and updates related to the fight against cybercrime in Europe.

WE NEED YOUR HELP, PLEASE GET IN TOUCH!
We seek coordinators from LEAs, industry / SMEs and Academia / Research, who share an interest and wish to contribute to different thematic subjects in the project.

Figure 4 Cyclopes leaflet and network leaflet (print versions)

Figure 5 Leaflets and roll-up in display at Octopus Conference in Bucharest, Romania, December 2023.

Poster

A CYCLOPES network poster was created (Figure 5) in collaboration with WP5 to be used in the EAFS22 conference as well as other events in the future. The poster contains similar information as the network leaflet except in a more graphical representation.

Figure 6 Cyclopes network poster

Roll-ups

The CYCLOPES Roll-up is one of the main materials designed to catch the attention of potential audiences especially when the audience is able to physically or digitally see them (Figure 6).

LAUREA and PPHS have jointly contributed towards the printing and sending copies to all partners for dissemination purposes.

Figure 7 CYCLOPES roll-ups

The roll-up has been displayed in several meetings, conferences, workshops and other events (Figure 7).

Figure 8 CYCLOPES booth with roll-ups & leaflets on display at Octopus conference in Bucharest, Romania, December 2023.

Flyers/Banners

For each CYCLOPES organised event such as joint live exercise, workshop or webinar, there was a flyer designed and published in all dissemination channels (Figure 8).

One banner is also created for the social media. This one displays a QR code that directs visitors to the network registration link in the project website (Figure 9).

Figure 9 CYCLOPES flyers dedicated to various events

Figure 10 CYCLOPES social media banner

Podcasts

Lead partner of WP6 offers technical capabilities and assistance for producing podcasts. Laurea sees highly beneficial to pilot a first podcast, and then depending on its success and resources to continue with it into a series. The podcasts will be used to communicate CYCLOPES activities and experiences learned from the project to both professionals and a wider audience.

Social media and stats

As we have seen through experience, social media platforms offer a great opportunity to target desired audiences to keep them updated with project progress. Their simplicity in publishing

content and their openness offer an easy way to reach audiences regardless of the device. The WP6 leader and the project coordinator have decided that for our specific project needs, LinkedIn and X accounts would be more favourable as opposed to Facebook, Instagram and other platforms.

During the second reporting period, we have developed a more structured approach to social media planning and posting. A new calendar-based solution helps to divide and plan the work better. Planning supports the quality of the work in social media. Also, to ensure awareness of and participation in the events, we are posting more frequently about events beforehand.

LinkedIn

The project dissemination team has dedicated a significant effort in reaching the targeted audiences via the social media platform. All public information has been shared regularly from the project including important sources of information from relevant clusters, partners and stakeholders.

During the second reporting period, the project has gained more followers and raised the number of impressions. The follower count has been continuously increasing on average 26 followers per month. Currently there are 761 followers (19.4.2024).

In the last 12 months of the reporting period there has been 120 posts with a combined impression stat of 29,755 as of 8.4.2024. Due to technical limitations we're unable to provide exact numbers for the first half a year of the reporting period. Based on average, we estimate the overall numbers for the reporting period to be 180 posts with combined impression stats of 44,633.

X

In similar fashion as the LinkedIn account, an X account has been created for the CYCLOPES project called project-cyclopes. Here too, information has been shared regularly as on other channels, however, X has been a little less impactful in amassing followers compared to the LinkedIn with 214 followers at the time of writing this report. The number of followers has doubled since the first reporting period, and the number of posts is also higher.

During the reporting period, the project has created a total of 63 posts which yielded a combined impressions stat of 7104. Due to technical challenges, the actual numbers were only available of 52 posts out of the 63. The missing impressions stats of 11 posts were calculated based on the average of the 52 posts ($5861/52=113$). Despite the significant lower number of posts compared to LinkedIn, it is still a good reach.

YouTube

We are in the process of creating a YouTube channel for the CYCLOPES project. YouTube is a popular choice for hosting video material, but it is also frequently used as a platform for podcasts. We believe that YouTube would be an effective channel of communication towards both wider audience and professionals interested in cybersecurity.

Dissemination events

During the reporting period, 2 dissemination events were organised. On the 21st of September 2023, the 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event was held online to stimulate dialogue on pressing security matters and crime issues. 99 people registered for the event, and the final audience consisted of 74 attendees from LEAs across Europe, industry and science as well

as relevant networks and organisations responsible for fighting cybercrime. The 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event is organised on the 16th to 17th of April in Vienna, Austria.

Publications

	Date (DD/MM/YY)	Author(s)	Title of Publication	Publisher	Link	Partner	Peer reviewed	Open access
	30.11.2022	HO	Practitioners' gaps and requirements - 1st Annual Report for Industry and Academia	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.11.2022	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Cybercrime relating to remote desktop protocol and other similar technologies	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.11.2022	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Digital forensics on mobile devices and wearable technologies	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.11.2022	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Social engineering to enable cybercrime	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.11.2022	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Automotive digital forensics	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.11.2022	ASI	First annual standardisation	LAUREA	Link to the public report	ASI	Yes	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669.

			recommendations					
	04.05.2023	LAUREA	Project Newsletter	LAUREA	Link to the newsletter	LAUREA	Yes	Yes
	30.06.2023	HO	Practitioners' gaps and requirements 2nd public available annual report for industry and academia	LAUREA	Link to official publication	HO	Yes	Yes
	24.10.2023	LAUREA	Project Newsletter	LAUREA	Link to the newsletter	LAUREA	Yes	Yes
	16.05.2022	PPHS	CINTiA 2023, Recapping the latest in criminal intelligence	LAUREA	Link to the public report	PPHS	Yes	Yes
	31.12.2023	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Cryptocurrency as a facilitator for cybercrime	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	31.12.2023	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Investigations involving cloud services	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	31.12.2023	HO	Gaps and needs of LEA practitioners in the area of: Internet of things devices	LAUREA	Link to the public report	HO	Yes	Yes
	30.06.2023	PPHS	Report from the second cyclopes annual webinar	LAUREA	Link to the public report	PPHS	Yes	Yes
	08.02.2024	LAUREA	Cybercrime as a global challenge: Insights from Octopus 2023	LAUREA	Link to the public report	LAUREA	Yes	Yes

	08.02.2024	LAUREA	Project Newsletter	LAUREA	Link to the newsletter	LAUREA	Yes	Yes
--	------------	--------	--------------------	--------	--	--------	-----	-----

Table 3 List of all project articles and publications in various channels

Newsletters

The official CYCLOPES website has a dedicated space where visitors can subscribe to the newsletter. The form is connected to the Brevo service which hosts the newsletter templates and acts as a mailing platform.

The newsletter (Figure 11) is dedicated to the wider audience with the aim to inform on latest project activities, planned events and any future work.

As of 9.4.2024 there are 348 newsletter subscribers on the database. 3 newsletters were delivered during this reporting period. In addition to the Brevo platform, the newsletter is also shared in all other project channels.

We have decided to produce the newsletter more frequently. The plan is to compile and send out the newsletter quarterly, depending on the number of CYCLOPES-related activities that have taken place. The latest newsletter has been published in February 2024.

We have also developed a new online form for our partners to submit their activities to the newsletter. This is more user-friendly to use compared to the Excel file we have been using.

Figure 11 CYCLOPES Newsletter

Articles

We have noticed a need to publish more about the project results to a wider audience. One article has already been published about insights of the Octopus conference in December 2023, and another publication has been delivered about CINTiA conference in September 2023.

Public versions of restricted reports

It was decided that due to the nature of the project deliverables being mostly restricted and as such unable to be shared with the public, we would put an effort into creating shortened public versions of such deliverables and reports with an appealing design in order to maximise the impact of the project towards the targeted audiences.

During the second reporting period, there have been eleven such publications delivered across all CYCLOPES channels. Such reports include but are not limited to: Workshop results, policy briefs, joint live exercise reports and selected deliverables (Figure 13).

Figure 12 Shortened public versions of restricted reports

Network members

Dissemination towards increasing the network membership has been promoted and ongoing throughout the majority of dissemination events, materials and channels. Currently these calls are ongoing on project’s social media, website, newsletters, leaflets, poster and so on.

Requests for membership can be made via the project’s website <https://www.cyclopes-project.eu/join-us>

Currently there are 260+ Individual members in the CYCLOPES network representing more than 100+ different organisations.

In the future, we will intensify our efforts at retaining members for the network via quality content on social media, newsletters, and other relevant platforms and media. We are also following more events within the field of cybercrime as means of securing new members.

Organised Webinars

The CYCLOPES project organises webinars annually. The 2nd CYCLOPES webinar was organised on the 7th of December 2023. The webinar had a theme ‘Enterprises as Victims of Cybercrime’ which was planned in cooperation with European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN). The event had 147 registered participants: LEAs, prosecutors and judicial experts across Europe and CYCLOPES Consortium members. The final audience of attending participants was 75.

Participation to other webinars

During this reporting period the CYCLOPES project has not participated to external webinars. As covid-19 situation has calmed, more events have been organised live instead of online.

External Dissemination Platforms

All results and public information are being actively shared in various platforms where CYCLOPES stakeholders may be reached. Most of these platforms are offered by European Commission and other EU LEA organisations.

The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS) ¹

The project has started using the ENLETS messaging system for its network members and sharing results with the already 462 LEA members as at the time of writing the report.

EU CIRCABC ²

CIRCABC platform is a space offered by European Union with the main aim to support information sharing and collaboration between various networks of practitioners. Currently, CYCLOPES is sharing information with over 50 representatives of approximately 25 NoPs, with two representatives as POC from each.

Europol Platform for Exports Forum ³

The SPACE subgroup has at least 8000 members, and so far more than 40 LEA representatives have requested access to our intermediate results.

As CYCLOPES is not a member of Europol, but we are operating within this platform via a partner organization that is a member. We are also working on getting a direct access.

Cybercrime Knowledge Exchange (Interpol)

We have been in contact with Cybercrime Knowledge Exchange and we are working on getting access to their platform as well.

Collaboration with other projects/networks

Cyberspace LEA Cluster

The project is a member of the Cyberspace LEA cluster (Figure 15) which includes over 20 projects that share similar objectives and stakeholders.

The overall objective of the cluster is the following:

1. To share knowledge in order to support law enforcement against money-laundering, cybercrime, organised crime and terrorism, for example, by webinars for the partners in the cluster.
2. To leverage our dissemination activities by mentioning the projects in the cluster on our websites, inviting articles from the cluster projects in our newsletter.
3. To ensure the coherence and complementarity of our recommendations to the EC, LEAs and other stakeholders, as far as possible.
4. To explore a degree of interoperability or compatibility between our technical platforms, modules and/or services.
5. To explore synergies, research opportunities and possible joint exploitation activities.

¹ <https://enlets.eu/>

² <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/welcome>

³ https://sts.europol.europa.eu/adfs/oauth2/authorize?scope=openid+email+profile&response_type=code&redirect_uri=https%3A%2F%2Fpe.europol.europa.eu%2Fportal%2Flogin%2Fopenidconnect&state=k0Zx5zloXefRF_Z05IQrpLIUCEldc08M-JdsHHop4EM&nonce=m7tuv8fz3AUucA3G-pcWCnJ8skJL79i_fz1Tk49inw4&client_id=PRD_EPE_ServerApp

Cooperation has been going on in accordance with the objectives.

Figure 13 Cyberspace LEA cluster

CERIS Community

The CYCLOPES project has attended CERIS events during the reporting period and has engaged directly with relevant projects and stakeholders from across Europe – informing them and updating them on related actions and activities. Although the project has not had a formal presentation – the awareness-raising is a useful tool to inform appropriate members of the research community about the tasks CYCLOPES is working on.

NOTIONES Project

CYCLOPES has initiated a partnership with the NOTIONES project. NOTIONES (iNteracting netwOrk of iTelligence and securITy practitiOners EU with iNdustry and acadEmia actorS) is a Horizon 2020 project establishing a network to connect researchers and industries with the intelligence community. NOTIONES focuses on facilitating exchange on new and emerging technologies but also aims to equip solution providers with insights on the corresponding needs and requirements of practitioners. The cooperation will include dissemination activities and organising webinars together.

Established Cooperation Partnerships

During the first year, most actions have evolved around gaining awareness and visibility; in the second year, focused on the implementation, the team invited and motivated practitioners and other stakeholders to have a more practical hands-on experience with the CYCLOPES activities. The project builds, strengthens and maintains links with the following key stakeholders and networks whose work is conducted in the areas relevant to CYCLOPES:

- European Commission, DG HOME
- European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EJCN),
- European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA),
- European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG),
- European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI),
- European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EUROPOL Innovation Lab.

Moreover, in the third year of the project implementation, a cooperation also with INTERPOL and CEPOL will be initiated.

The cooperation with the above networks and stakeholders is foreseen through exchanging information about the ongoing and planned activities, particularly workshops, surveys/questionnaires, conferences, etc. The exchange of selected reports and other project outcomes relevant for both parties, and the synchronisation of conducted actions, should help avoid duplicating and overlapping work.

3. Dissemination KPIs Analysis

The Dissemination and Communication Plan defines the tools for measuring the success of dissemination efforts in different stages of the project. These guidelines include a set of KPIs which were created by the WP6 leader in cooperation with the project coordinator. The KPIs help us to understand the direction the project is going by defining requirements in several steps of dissemination and support us to understand what corrective measures are necessary for the future. The KPIs (Table 4) are reviewed at several intervals during the lifetime of the project, and they have been recently updated to the D6.2 Updated Dissemination and Communication (DC) Plan in order to reflect a more realistic approach in accordance with project scope.

In order to measure the performance of the KPIs, a colour scheme has been chosen each determining the level of performance:

- Green – The KPI is met or exceeded
- Yellow – The KPI has met the average level and there is room for improvement
- Grey – The KPI has met the low level of expectation and improvements are recommended.

Table 4 Dissemination KPI analysis

		Target			
KPIs		Level of performance			
D&C Tools	Definition of indicator	Poor	Good	Excellent	Remarks
Project Website	The number of visits	Less than 100 per month	100-200 per month	more than 200 per month	The website has served 7,720 sessions in the current period (1.11.2022 – 17.4.2024.)

	The number of page views	Less than 200 per month	200-400 per month	more than 400 per month	The website has had over 16,659 page views during the course of the period
	Average time spent on website	Less than 15 sec.	15 sec. – 1 min.	more than 1 min.	The average time spent on the website is 1:14 min.
Social Media	Followers on LinkedIn	Less than 50 per year	80 on yearly basis	More than 80 on yearly basis	There are over 700 followers in total and over 300 new in the last 12 months.
	Followers on X	Less than 50 per year	50 on yearly basis	more than 50 on yearly basis	There are over 200 followers in total, and more 100 gained in the last 1,5 years.
	Number of posts	Less than 3 per month	3-5 per month	More than 5 per month	There have been approximately 180 posts during the reporting period on LKDIN and over 60 on X.
Annual Joint Live Exercises	Number of practitioners per event	Less than 10 per event	10-15 per event	More than 15 per event	Joint Live Exercises were organised in Croatia, in April 2023. There were 40 participants.
	Number of participants from the scientific community per event	Less than 3 per event	3-5 per event	More than 5 per event	-
	Number of participants from the Industry/SME per event	less than 3 per event	3-5 per event	More than 5 per event	-
Annual Dissemination Event	Number of participants per event	less than 30 per event	30-50 per event	more than 50 per event	There were over 70 participants in the first Dissemination Event in this reporting period. No data yet available on the second one (16.-17.4.24)
Annual Standardisation Workshop	Number of participants per event	less than 10 per event	10-30 per event	more than 30 per event	Two standardisation workshops are organised during this reporting period. One online on 24 th January 2023, second one in Vienna on 17 th

					April 2024. No data on the number of participants was available at the time of writing the deliverable
Practitioner Workshops	Number of participants per workshop	Less than 10 (online) Less than 7 (physical)	10-15 (Online) 7-12 (physical)	More than 15 (online) More than 12 (physical)	There have been 5 practitioner workshops during this period. With average 15-20 participants per workshops
Participation to External Events	Number of external events in which CYCLOPES participates	less than 3 per year	3-5 per year	more than 5 per year	There have been more than 20 external events during the period.
Liaison Activities and Synergies	Number of relevant projects/initiatives identified and contacted/invited at project events	Less than 4 on yearly basis	4-6 on yearly basis	more than 6 on yearly basis	Over 25 have been contacted and invited to the project events.
	Number of relevant organisations/communities/experts identified and contacted/invited at project events	less than 5 on yearly basis	5-10 on a yearly basis	More than 10 on a yearly basis	There have been over 13 organisations that have been contacted to establish cooperation.
	Number of cooperation activities (common events and other clustering activities)	less than 1 on a yearly basis	2-3 on a yearly basis	more than 3 on a yearly basis	There have been at least 3 in the period.
Link to the Community of Users	Number of 'CYCLOPES' presentations made during plenary meetings and thematic workshops	2 per year	2-3 per year	more than 3 per year	At least 10 different events throughout the last period.
Webinars	participants to the webinars	15-20 per webinar or less	20-30 per webinar	more than 30 per webinar	One webinar was organised and it had 147 registered participants and the final audience of attending participants was 75.
Newsletters	Newsletters published	Less than 2 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	3 newsletters have been published during this reporting period.
	Subscribers	20-50	50-100	more than 100	Currently there are 348 Newsletter subscribers.
CYCLOPES Community of Users	Number of new members (organisations not individuals)	0-5 per year	5-10 per year	more than 10 per year	The number has grown from 38 to over 100 organisations.

4. Conclusion and future recommendations

During the second reporting period, the project has been quite successful in reaching the targeted audiences. The CYCLOPES community has grown substantially, and the project has been actively disseminated in various channels. All public information has been shared to several channels and platforms where targeted audiences have been reached. Especially the LEA community.

Compared to the previous period, the Industry community reach has seen improvement. We see this increase via the attendance at CYCLOPES events, especially at the latest dissemination event held in April. Moreover we see the engagement on Social media (LinkedIn). Similarly, cooperating with other projects similar to Tools4Leas has seen an increase of the industry engagement as well. This target audience needs to be further increased and retained especially if the project aims to bring the industry closer to LEAs for innovation and capacity building potential.

We have continued publishing shortened public versions of classified reports. 11 such reports have been published during this reporting period. These are seen as excellent opportunities to disseminate about project results to the wider audience.

In the previous period the project almost reached the foreseen sessions on the website. During this period, the number is surpassed significantly. The dissemination efforts have been successful in this regard and we expect either a retention of the current ratio or a slight increase in the coming period.

Workshops and other events organised had now sufficient time for preparation compared to the previous one and this resulted in higher engagement from the audience. Worth to mention is that despite the higher attention, the project is limited to an average 15-20 participants per event due to quality reasons.

With the increase of dissemination efforts both within and beyond what the project envisioned it is evident that interest in the project activities and results among the targeted audiences has increased significantly. There is already a base of regular participants established and is being filled with new ones as time progresses.

The extended cooperation with other networks and organisations has been largely successful and the project sees that this trend will be increasing.

List of Figures

- Figure 1 An example of other events where CYCLOPES participants have represented the project.11
- Figure 2 Overall website audience analytics12
- Figure 3 Overall audience of the website by country13
- Figure 4 Cyclopes leaflet and network leaflet (print versions)14
- Figure 5 Leaflets and roll-up in display at Octopus Conference in Bucharest, Romania, December 2023.....15
- Figure 6 Cyclopes network poster15
- Figure 7 CYCLOPES roll-ups16
- Figure 8 CYCLOPES booth with roll-ups & leaflets on display at Octopus conference in Bucharest, Romania, December 2023.....16
- Figure 9 CYCLOPES flyers dedicated to various events17
- Figure 10 CYCLOPES social media banner17
- Figure 11 CYCLOPES Newsletter23
- Figure 12 Shortened public versions of restricted reports24
- Figure 13 Cyberspace LEA cluster26

List of Tables

- Table 1 Summary of Dissemination Activities 6
- Table 2 List of external dissemination events where CYCLOPES has been represented 7
- Table 3 List of all project articles and publications in various channels.....22
- Table 4 Dissemination KPI analysis27